

Synthesis and Antibacterial Activity of some Substituted Thioaryl and Arylsulphonylbenzo[*h*]quinolines

R. P. BAHUGUNA

Department of Chemistry, H. N. Bahuguna Garhwal University, Srinagar-246 174

Manuscript received 22 may 1992, revised 15 February 1995, accepted 3 April 1995

In consideration of antimicrobial and other medicinal properties of a number of substituted benzoquinolines¹, heterocyclic sulphides and sulphones^{2,3}, the present investigation reports some heterocyclic sulphides and sulphones incorporating benzoquinoline moiety.

The sulphides (3, 4) have been obtained from 2-chloro-4-methylbenzo[*h*]quinoline (1) and the sulphides (7, 8) obtained from 4-chloro-2-methylbenzo[*h*]quinoline (2) as shown in Scheme 1. The sulphides were converted to the corresponding sulphones by the oxidation with 1% KMnO₄.

The antibacterial activity of eight compounds was studied against Gram-positive *Staphylococcus aureus*, and Gram-negative *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* in concentration of 150 µg ml⁻¹ by disc assay method³.

After comparing the antibacterial action of the compounds on different bacteria and determining the minimum inhibitory zones, the activities (MIC) of the compounds were found to follow the order : 5, 9 > 6, 10 > 3, 7 > 4, 8.

Experimental

2-(*p*-Aminothiophenyl)-4-methylbenzo[*h*]quinoline (3) :

Scheme 1

Compound 1 (0.05 mol) dissolved in DMF (15–20 ml) was added to sodium salt of thiophenol² (a, 0.06 mol) and the mixture was refluxed for 15 h. The completion of the reac-

TABLE 1—SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3–10*

Compd. no	M.p. °C	ν _{max} (cm ⁻¹)	δ	δ	δ
			ArH	=C-CH ₃	Ar-NH ₂
3	165	1 600–1 450(aromatic), 650, 610(C=S), 3 400–3 250(NH ₂), 1 342–1 266 (C=N), 1 180, 1 125, 1 077 (substituted aryl ring) 860 (C-H)	6.6–8.1 (10H, m), 9.20 (1H, bs)	2.70(3H, s)	4–4.7 (2H, s)
4	232	1 600–1 450(aromatic), 650, 605 (C=S), 1 550, 1 365(NO ₂), 1 180, 1 130, 1 075 (substituted aryl ring), 850 (C-H)	6.85–8.3 (10H, m), 9.30 (1H, bs)	2.80(3H, s)	–
5	185	1 600–1 450(aromatic), 1 350, 1 145(SO ₂), 660, 620(C=S), 3 410–3 250(NH ₂), 1 170, 1 120, 1 080 (substituted aryl ring), 862 (C-H), 1 340–1 260(C=N)	7.7–8.2 (10H, m), 9.40 (1H, bs)	2.80(3H, s)	4.5(2H, s)
6	192	1 600–1 450(aromatic), 1 555, 1 360(NO ₂), 1 355–1 140(SO ₂), 1 180, 1 132, 1 070 (substituted aryl ring), 860 (C-H)	7.90–8.4 (10H, m), 9.40 (1H, bs)	2.90(3H, s)	–
7	200	1 600–1 450(aromatic), 650, 605 (C=S), 3 400–3 250(NH ₂), 1 190, 1 130, 1 080 (substituted aryl ring), 855 (C-H), 1 345–1 270 (C=N)	6.6–8.1 (10H, m), 9.20 (1H, bs)	2.70(3H, s)	4.4.7 (2H, s)
8	230	1 600–1 450(aromatic), 655, 610 (C=S), 1 550, 1 365 (NO ₂), 1 180, 1 132, 1 070 (substituted aryl ring), 855 (C-H)	6.85–8.3 (1H, m), 9.30 (1H, bs)	2.80(3H, s)	–
9	175	1 600–1 450(aromatic), 1 355, 1 145(SO ₂), 655, 620 (C=S), 3 410–3 250 (NH ₂), 1 185, 1 130, 1 085 (substituted aryl ring), 862 (C-H), 1 342–1 270 (C=N)	9.90–8.2 (10H, m), 9.40 (1H, bs)	2.80(3H, s)	4.5 (2H, s)
10	190	1 600–1 450(aromatic), 1 350, 1 140(SO ₂), 650, 615 (C=S), 1 555, 1 360(NO ₂), 1 175, 1 130, 1 080 (substituted aryl ring), 860 (C-H)	7.90–8.2 (10H, m), 9.40 (1H, bs)	2.90(3H, s)	–

NOTE

tion was checked as usual by tlc. The reaction mixture was poured on crushed ice and the resulting solid was dried and crystallised from a mixture of petroleum ether and acetone (1 : 9) as prismatic yellow crystals (70%), m.p. 165°. Similarly, the sulphides (**4**, **7**, **8**; yields 55–75%) were obtained using appropriate reactants (Table 1).

2-(p-Aminobenzene-sulphonyl)-4-methylbenzo[h]quinoline (5): To a solution of **3** (0.005 mol) in glacial acetic acid (15–20 ml), KMnO_4 solution (1%) was added with occasional shaking till it was in excess. Ethanol was added to the reaction mixture and the reaction mixture was poured in ice-cold water and filtered. The residue was extracted with hot acetone. After removal of the solvent, the residue was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) as colourless shining crystals (80%), m.p. 185° (Found : S, 9.10; N, 8.00. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$ requires : S, 9.10; N, 8.4%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1600–1450 (aromatic), 660, 620 (C=S), 3 410–3 250 (NH_2), 1 170, 1 120, 1

080 (substituted aryl ring) and 862 cm^{-1} (C-H out-of-plane); δ (CDCl_3) 7.7–8.2 (10H, m, ArH), 9.40 (1H, bs, ArH, shifted downfield due to more electron-attracting sulphonyl), 2.80 (H, s, =C- CH_3) and 4.5 (2H, s, NH_2). Similarly, other sulphones (**6**, **9**, **10**; yields 75–80%) were prepared (Table 1).

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Prof. B. C. Joshi for providing spectra and to Prof. H. N. Mangal, SMS College, Jaipur, for helping in antibacterial studies.

References

- 1 F GIAIDI and R PONCI, *Ann Chim (Rome)*, 1959, **49**, 606, H HOHNSTON and S H RUCTMAN, *Chem Abstr*, 1971, **74**, 31692
- 2 R P BAHUGUNA and B C JOSHI *Acta Chentia Indica*, 1980, **3**, 116
- 3 R P BAHUGUNA, B C JOSHI and H N MANGAL, *J Inst Chem (Calcutta)*, 1984, **56**, 185